

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FORTICH****FIRST NAME: DENNIS****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on MacOS 10)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As I was going through the course materials, I noticed that essay writing is an essential component in my doctoral coursework here at Euclid University. As an evaluative tool to demonstrate my understanding and academic writing skills on the assigned course material, it is crucial for me to have a better grasp of the essential concepts of academic writing. Although essay writing is often treated with a certain amount of trepidation by most students, this approach has been commonly used by other institutions to allow professors to assess the students' skills as writers and critical thinkers (Norton 1990, 411). This exercise has enabled me to reflect seriously on contentious issues of essay writing. The ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1 material provided me a step-by-step formula on how to write academic essays effectively with considerations on structure, plagiarism, and citation from a critical & creative viewpoint (EUCLID 2015, 2–18). This article presents a framework for understanding essential concepts of academic writing.

2) THE FORMULA

According to Euclid course material, there are three structural components of an essay: an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. An introduction presents a general idea into specific views; the body then elaborates these views with supporting evidence; and the conclusion wraps up these specific views into a general idea based on the argumentative position of the writer (EUCLID 2015, 4). Furthermore, Barbara emphasized that understanding the problem, charting the issues, establishing the core essay, and revising to finalize the theme are four fundamental steps of essay writing

(Risser 1977, 56). To start a well-structured essay, understanding every aspect of the question is crucial in developing a concise thesis statement. It is essential that the question must be scrutinized by taking note of the first sentence and its keywords. The writer then formulates his initial viewpoint based on his own knowledge as an initial response to the question which will become the thesis statement. This thesis statement will then serve as the starting point for the essay. This thesis statement will allow guidance for the research work and serve as a platform for discussion points grounded on reason and evidence; however, this demands supporting literary evidence. To support the thesis statement, research work will play a vital role in developing the body of an academic essay (EUCLID 2015, 2–3). Since academic writing is an evidence-based article, researching will enable students to gather more extensive views from different authors, and gain shreds of evidence to support the students' argumentative position that allows them to develop discussion points (EUCLID 2015, 3). According to Robert, asking "why" will help expand and add depth on the discussion points of the core essay (Rider and Roberts 2001, 27). In my opinion, this information can be organized into "concept maps," which is a visual organization of ideas to quickly pinpoint suggested relationships between different views from several sources within the context of the thesis statement. These statements are strategically arranged within a paragraph into a topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, and then an analysis statement, respectively (EUCLID 2015, 4).

a) Plagiarism

Since essay writing involves a gathering of information from several sources to support a particular viewpoint, plagiarism is a common concern among academic writers. From an academic standpoint, plagiarism is considered a severe offense and is highly unethical in any educational institution (EUCLID 2015, 8–12). According to Newton (2001), the most common form of plagiarism among students is leaving out the citations and footnotes on any completed article (171). Any actions that involve presenting someone else's idea or work without crediting the literary source is considered plagiarism. In other words, plagiarism is a fraudulent act that consists of stealing and then lying about it afterward (What Is Plagiarism? - Plagiarism.Org n.d.). To avoid such offense, proper citation of the author or source is obligatory (EUCLID 2015, 13).

b) Citation Styles

Citations are placed within the body (in-text citation) and at the end (list of work cited) of the article itself. The "in-text citation" provides brief documentation of the literary source within the text. It requires the author's name and page number in parenthesis after the sentence. The in-text citation can be employed using three methods: quotation, paraphrasing, or signal phrasing. To use the quotation method, the writer must capture the exact words of the author in the sentence using a quotation mark. This method is often applied when you intend to communicate a strong statement that is only emphasized using exact quotes from the source, or when the statement is from a person of authority that can be useful leverage to convince readers about specific issues. However,

the overuse of a quotation method does not look good in any research article because it makes the material less original; thus it is more appropriate to use paraphrasing method by using the author's idea in your own words. The paraphrasing method employs an accurate representation of the author's view but using your personal style and word choices (EUCLID 2015, 23–24). Both quotation and paraphrasing methods will cite the author's name and page number, unlike the signal phrasing method of which only the page number is in parenthesis. Signal phrasing already mentions the author's name at the beginning of the sentence, followed by a signaling verb (EUCLID 2015, 32).

In contrast, the "list of work cited" is a detailed bibliographic listing of all sources cited in the article following a specific format (e.g., Authors Name. Book Title. Place of Publication: Publisher, Date). Although it is recommended to cite every source in the article, any information that is already common knowledge is an exception to the rule. Meaning, any information that is repeated in different sources can be considered as common knowledge and need not be included in the citations (EUCLID 2015, 13–30).

3) CONCLUSION

Before any student can be creative in essay writing, they must first be familiar with the structure until it becomes second nature to them to allow them to experiment with new ideas within their basic framework (Risser 1977, 56). Although I don't have extensive experience in essay writing, this response paper has provided me a structured refresher on the essential fundamentals of academic writing. These essential concepts include understanding the question and using the initial response to that question to help develop a thesis statement. This thesis statement will then define the structure and flow of ideas from relevant sources to support its argumentative position. Since an essay is a collective view of an idea from several sources with the intent to persuade readers about a particular topic, a citation is an imperative academic policy to avoid plagiarism at all costs. Therefore, every submitted article must have an "in-text" citation and "list-of-work" citation. The in-text citations can either be in the form of a quotation, paraphrase, or signal phrase. To have a coherent flow of ideas, each paragraph must be arranged with a topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, and a summarized analysis respectively. Although an argumentative essay is seen as a critical and creative example of a written material, most students still hold two common conceptions: essay as a viewpoint, and essay as an arrangement (Norton 1990, 411).

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